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Canopy development, leaf traits and yield in high altitude Andean maize under contrasting plant densities in Argentina

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Abstract:	<p>In highlands, the increase in altitude results in a drastic decrease in temperature (T) that delays phenological development of maize, decreasing light interception during the cycle. This could be partially overcome by increasing plant density, but information is scarce for designing specific management options. The objective of this work was to describe changes in canopy development, photosynthetic performance, biomass and yield of maize grown at contrasting plant densities (5.7 plants m⁻², locally used, and 8.7 plants m⁻², 50% higher). Three experiments were carried out in two high altitude environments within the Argentinean Andean region, Hornillos (HOR, 2380 masl, 2019-20 and 2020-21) and El Rosal (ERO, 3350 masl, 2019-20), and complementary data was obtained from samplings in 8 farmer's fields (from 2400 to 3400 masl, 2022-23). In the experiments, mean T during the first 150 days of the cycle was 33% lower at ERO, which implied 39 extra days but 25% shorter thermal time to achieve silking. The higher plant density significantly increased leaf area index and light interception at ERO, whereas at HOR, this was only evident during the second season. At the leaf level, plants grown at ERO had thicker leaves with higher chlorophyll (+36%) and nitrogen (40%) content. Photosynthetic electron transport rate at full irradiance was +20% higher at ERO but significantly varied throughout the day with lowest values at the morning, which was not observed at HOR and was not related to light intensity or stomatal conductance. At HOR, the increase in plant density did not improve light interception, nor yield in 2019-20 (with average yields of 6356 kg ha⁻¹) but it did improve both in 2020-21 when generally lower yields were attained (4821 kg ha⁻¹). Across farmer's fields, increasing densities consistently reduced yield per plant ($r^2=0.57^{***}$) but improved yield per area basis, that was maximized at 10 pl m⁻² as a result of a steady increase in kernel number m⁻² (up to 15 pl m⁻²). Thus, in these high altitude environments, increasing plant density beyond recommended (6 pl m⁻²) is a</p>

	promising approach for improving yield, with major penalties of supra-optimum densities being related with kernel weight. Further work is needed to explore the effect of different factors limiting kernel growth, over plant density responses.
Keywords:	maize; altitude; density

Dr. Rafael Ribeiro
Editor
Experimental Agriculture

October 17th, 2023

Dear Dr. Rafael Ribeiro

I am pleased to submit our article ‘Canopy development, leaf traits and yield under contrasting plant densities in high altitude Andean maize in Argentina’ by D.A. Salve, M.L. Maydup, G.A. Salazar, E.A. Tambussi and M. Antonietta to be considered for publication in Experimental Agriculture.

This manuscript has been previously reviewed under the number EAG-D-23-00080. In this new version we have addressed all the minor comments detailed below. We hope the manuscript is now suitable for publication.

Kind regards,

Mariana Antonietta
antoniettamariana@gmail.com

Ref.: Ms. No. EAG-D-23-00132

Canopy development, leaf traits and yield in high altitude Andean maize under contrasting plant densities in Argentina

Dear Dr. Antonietta,

We are very pleased to inform you that your paper entitled Canopy development, leaf traits and yield in high altitude Andean maize under contrasting plant densities in Argentina has been conditionally accepted pending you make the following changes.

- at the end of Summary, you mentioned that increasing density reduces many yield components but concluded with an indication of increasing density. Please, re-phrase this and avoid any misunderstanding. For instance, you can mention that yield on plant basis is reduced but the overall yield on area basis is increased.

We have rephrased this for more clarity.

- please, use kg instead of Kg along the paper (including text, tables and figures).

We have corrected this throughout the manuscript.

- when citing suppl. material, you should write at the first time Suppl. Material Fig. S1 (or S2, S3) or Table S1. Then, only Fig. S1 (or S2, S3) or Table S1. Please, revise the paper and adjust this.

We have corrected this throughout the manuscript.

- check oCd (without dot) along the entire paper.

We have corrected this throughout the manuscript.

- Fig. 1: is time missing in units of y-axis in Fig. 1D? Should it be MJ m⁻² d⁻¹?

Thanks for noticing this mistake, we have corrected this accordingly.

- Figs. 3 and 4: use mol instead of moles for ETR and PAR.

We have corrected this in both figures.

1 **Running title**

2 Responses to plant density in Andean maize

3

4 **Title**

5 **Canopy development, leaf traits and yield in high altitude Andean maize under**
6 **contrasting plant densities in Argentina**

7

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18

19 **SUMMARY**

20

21 In highlands, the increase in altitude results in a drastic decrease in temperature (T) that
22 delays phenological development of maize, decreasing light interception during the
23 cycle. This could be partially overcome by increasing plant density, but information is
24 scarce for designing specific management options. The objective of this work was to
25 describe changes in canopy development, photosynthetic performance, biomass and
26 yield of maize grown at contrasting plant densities (5.7 plants m⁻², locally used, and 8.7
27 plants m⁻², 50% higher). Three experiments were carried out in two high altitude
28 environments within the Argentinean Andean region, Hornillos (HOR, 2380 masl,
29 2019-20 and 2020-21) and El Rosal (ERO, 3350 masl, 2019-20), and complementary
30 data was obtained from samplings in 8 farmer's fields (from 2400 to 3400 masl, 2022-
31 23). In the experiments, mean T during the first 150 days of the cycle was 33% lower at
32 ERO, which implied 39 extra days but 25% shorter thermal time to achieve silking. The
33 higher plant density significantly increased leaf area index and light interception at
34 ERO, whereas at HOR, this was only evident during the second season. At the leaf

35 level, plants grown at ERO had thicker leaves with higher chlorophyll (+36%) and
36 nitrogen (40%) content. Photosynthetic electron transport rate at full irradiance was
37 +20% higher at ERO but significantly varied throughout the day with lowest values at
38 the morning, which was not observed at HOR and was not related to light intensity or
39 stomatal conductance. At HOR, the increase in plant density did not improve light
40 interception, nor yield in 2019-20 (with average yields of 6356 kg ha⁻¹) but it did
41 improve both in 2020-21 when generally lower yields were attained (4821 kg ha⁻¹).
42 Across farmer's fields, increasing densities consistently reduced yield per plant
43 ($r^2=0.57***$) but improved yield per area basis, that was maximized at 10 pl m⁻² as a
44 result of a steady increase in kernel number m⁻² (up to 15 pl m⁻²). Thus, in these high
45 altitude environments, increasing plant density beyond recommended (6 pl m⁻²) is a
46 promising approach for improving yield, with major penalties of supra-optimum
47 densities being related with kernel weight. Further work is needed to explore the effect
48 of different factors limiting kernel growth, over plant density responses.

49

50 INTRODUCTION

51

52 Worldwide, family and indigenous agriculture provide around 56% of basic food
53 products but occupies barely 20% of the available arable land (Gornitzky, 2015), most
54 of which is marginal in terms of yield potential of main crops. In the Northwest of
55 Argentina (NWA), yields are limited by the natural conditions of the highlands (those
56 located at least 1000 meters above the sea level, masl) characterized by low air
57 temperature (T) which decreases with an average rate of 0.55°C for every 100 m
58 (Körner, 2003). On the contrary, in the NWA solar radiation can be 30% higher during
59 summer at 3350 compared with 1150 masl in locations at similar latitude, partly due to
60 increased UV (Utrillas *et al.*, 2018). Most cropped species in the NWA are maize,
61 quinoa and Andean potato (www.siiia.gov.ar) among which maize is the only one with a
62 C₄ photosynthetic metabolism, implying higher sensibility to low T but, at the same
63 time, a higher response to increasing irradiances (Muchow *et al.*, 1990; Andrade, 1995).
64 Available information regarding the compound effects of altitude over maize crops is
65 scarce, and more studies are needed to develop specific management strategies for
66 maize in these environments.

67 At increasing altitudes, the decrease in mean T implies a shortening of the frost-free
68 period and a concomitant delay in sowing date, which reduces the crop cycle duration

69 and, with this, the light interception throughout it. After sowing, low temperatures
70 extend the duration in days of phenological stages (Ritchie *et al.*, 1989), with
71 differences of up to 80 days in crop cycle duration between sites differing in 1000 m of
72 altitude (Cooper, 1979). This implies a delay in achieving maximum leaf area index
73 (LAI), resulting in further reductions in light interception and biomass accumulation
74 with increasing altitude (Cooper, 1979; Pace, 2019). At the same time, the decrease in T
75 with increasing altitude will also extend the duration of the critical period, and with this,
76 the light interception during this period which could finally result in a larger grain
77 number (Andrade *et al.*, 1999). Consistently, increasing night T during the critical
78 period (+5°C with maximum night T of 25°C) results in a shortening of this stage and a
79 lower grain number (Cantarero *et al.*, 1999).

80 Among the environmental factors affecting photosynthesis, low night temperatures can
81 reduce maize photosynthesis up to 30%, especially in the early morning (Ying *et al.*,
82 2000; Kosová *et al.*, 2005). Also, the lower atmospheric pressure typical of high altitude
83 environments can reduce the CO₂ diffusion rates to chloroplasts (Körner, 2007) and
84 lower vapour pressure deficits (typical in the NWA) may promote stomatal closure
85 regardless of the plant water status, implying CO₂ limitations for photosynthesis even in
86 C₄ species (Hirasawa y Hsiao, 1999). On the other hand, higher irradiance with
87 increasing altitude could represent an advantage for maize, whose photosynthesis at the
88 leaf level saturates beyond 2000 $\mu\text{moles photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Chen *et al.*, 2014).

89 Part of these negative environmental effects could be mitigated by increasing plant
90 density, which is an important management variable in maize (Maddonni *et al.*, 2001;
91 Tokatlidis *et al.*, 2004). A higher plant density could partially overcome the delayed
92 crop phenology, allowing an earlier achievement of maximum leaf area index further
93 benefitted from the larger radiation input, whereas detrimental effects over grain
94 number could be compensated for by an extended duration of the critical period. The
95 objective of this work is to evaluate canopy development, light interception, leaf traits,
96 photosynthetic performance and yield of Andean maize cropped in highlands under
97 contrasting plant densities.

98

99 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

100

101 *Experimental design*

102 Experiments were conducted in two sites of NWA located at different altitudes. One of
103 the sites was in Hornillos (hereafter, HOR), Jujuy province, at 2380 masl (23.65° S.
104 65.43° W) within the Instituto de Investigación y Desarrollo Tecnológico para la
105 Agricultura Familiar del Noroeste Argentino, IPAF NOA (Institute for Smallholders
106 Agriculture of the Northwest of Argentina) which belongs to the Instituto Nacional de
107 Tecnología Agropecuaria, INTA (National Institute of Agricultural Technology). The
108 other site was in an annexed field of the Elementary School at El Rosal (hereafter,
109 ERO), Salta province, at 3350 masl (24.38° S. 65.77° W). At each site, treatments
110 consisted of two contrasting planting densities: 5.7 and 8.6 plants m⁻². The low density
111 corresponded to the recommended density for these environments (Gómez and Macedo,
112 2011) whereas 8.6 plants m⁻² is 50% higher than recommended. An open-pollinated line
113 called “creole yellow corn” was sown at both sites, and “white corn” was also included
114 at HOR. Both genotypes are usually cropped by farmers within this altitudinal range
115 and have been widely known as local races (Cámara Hernandez *et al.*, 2011). Seeds
116 were obtained from the INTA seed multiplication program. Soil samples were taken at
117 each site and classified as sandy loam at HOR and sandy at ERO (Suppl. Material Table
118 S1). Both soils had high values of organic matter (>2.8%), and similar pH values and
119 carbon/N relationships.

120

121 *Crop management*

122 Previous crop was Andean potato at ERO and quinoa and amaranth at HOR in the first
123 season, and maize at HOR in the second season. Approximately 30 days before sowing
124 dry goat guano was applied at an estimated rate of 1 kg m⁻² in both sites, which is
125 similar to rates used by local farmers (Gómez and Macedo, 2011). Guano chemical
126 composition was analysed in 2019 in the laboratory of the Universidad Nacional de
127 Jujuy (National University of Jujuy), allowing to estimate a rate of 187 kg ha⁻¹ of
128 nitrogen and 174 ppm of extractable phosphorus applied. Treatments were laid out in
129 three blocks (four blocks in HOR in the second season) and densities were randomly
130 distributed in plots within each block at each site. At HOR, genotypes were distributed
131 in subplots within each plant density. Each plot (ERO) or subplot (HOR) consisted of 4
132 rows 0.7 m apart and 4 m long (11.2 m²). Seeds were sown manually on October 29th at
133 HOR and October 31st at ERO in 2019 and on December 2nd at HOR in 2020. Three
134 seeds were placed in each hill and then thinned to the aimed density after emergence.
135 The crop was maintained free of weeds and insects using conventional agrochemicals

136 when necessary and was irrigated as needed from emergence using ditch irrigation at
137 HOR and drip irrigation at ERO. Previous work indicates that nitrogen leaching is
138 higher under ditch irrigation and water use efficiency is lower compared with drip
139 irrigation (Li *et al.*, 2020). However, these effects can be negligible in our work, since
140 organic fertilizer was used (less prone to leaching) and water offer was enough to
141 prevent water stress symptoms throughout the cycle.

142

143 *Meteorological conditions*

144 At HOR, T was registered by a meteorological station 100 m away from the
145 experimental field. At ERO, T was registered by a thermocouple placed in a
146 meteorological shelter; however, due to technical problems, gaps arised in the series of
147 measured data. To fill these gaps, the hourly values estimated by the SOLCAST satellite
148 database (<https://solcast.com/>) have been used, after a correction by linear
149 approximation based on correlations between measured hourly T values and the
150 SOLCAST values (only valid for summertime):

$$151 \quad T_{\text{ERO}} (\text{°C}) = 1.56 * T_{\text{SOLCAST}} (\text{°C}) - 1.37 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

152 Solar radiation was also estimated using the SOLCAST model. Thermal time
153 computations started at sowing, using mean daily air T and a base T of 8°C (Ritchie and
154 NeSmith, 1991) whereas mean temperatures never exceeded the optimum T for maize
155 growth (34°C, Wilkens and Singh, 2003). Thus, we used a simple linear model to
156 calculate thermal time, which was expressed as the sum of °C day⁻¹ (Cd).

157

158 *Non-destructive determinations*

159 In each site, 6 consecutive plants within the central rows of each plot were tagged at the
160 V3 stage for non-destructive determinations. Crop phenology was determined in the
161 tagged plants following the scale proposed by Ritchie *et al.* (1989). Leaf area was
162 assessed non-destructively by measuring the maximum length and width of each leaf
163 and multiplying it by 0.75 as in Montgomery (1911) so that:

$$164 \quad \text{Individual leaf area} = \text{length} \times \text{width} \times 0.75. \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

165 Leaf area index (LAI) was then calculated as the sum of the area of all the leaves of
166 each plant multiplied by plant density. After flowering, a visual register of canopy
167 senescence was done weekly and the area of senesced leaves (with more than 50% of its
168 area yellowed) were subtracted from the LAI maximum achieved at flowering.

169

170 *Chlorophyll content, specific leaf area and leaf N content*

171 Different leaf traits were measured in leaves representing different canopy positions.
172 The leaves measured were the third leaf above the main ear, representing an apical leaf,
173 the leaf adjacent to the ear, representing a middle-positioned leaf, and the leaf
174 positioned three leaves below the ear leaf, representing a basal leaf. In some plants, the
175 ear bud was still not visible by the time of sampling; in these cases the leaf below the
176 topmost expanded leaf was considered the apical leaf, going downwards every 3
177 nodes for middle and basal leaves. Chlorophyll content was assessed using a SPAD 502
178 (Minolta, EEUU). At least five measurements across the leaf blade were made and
179 averaged, and three plants per plot (9 plants per treatment) were measured.

180 In these same leaf positions, specific leaf area was determined by punching 6 cm² at the
181 mid third of each leaf thrice (*i.e.*, 18 cm² per leaf). Samples were obtained from 2 plants
182 per plot (6 plants per treatment). Leaf discs were dried in an oven at 60°C until constant
183 weight and weighed. Specific leaf area was calculated as the quotient between the area
184 of each leaf sample and the respective dry weight.

185 After specific leaf area was assessed, the same samples were utilized to determine leaf
186 N content. A compound sample obtained from 2 plants per plot (3 replicates per each
187 site x plant density x leaf position combination) was used for micro-Kjeldahl analyses
188 using a Hanon equipment (Nade, K9840) following conventional protocols for digestion
189 and distillation of the samples.

190

191 *Chlorophyll fluorescence measurements and stomatal conductance*

192 Simultaneous photosynthetic electron transport rate (ETR) and stomatal conductance
193 (gs) measurements were taken during 2 clear-sky days and at three times during the day:
194 morning (09:00–11:00 hs), midday (12:00–14:00 hs) and afternoon (15:00–17:00 hs).
195 Measurements were taken in apical, middle and basal leaves, representing different
196 positions within the canopy (see above).

197 The effective photosystem II quantum yield was measured using a pulse-amplitude
198 modulated FMS2 chlorophyll fluorometer (Hansatech, UK). Each measurement was
199 done in 3 plants per plot (9 plants per treatment) in fully illuminated spots around a
200 middle position of the leaf lamina between the midrib and the leaf margin. Thus,
201 measurements are an estimation of the photosynthetic potential of each leaf at each time
202 of the day but do not account for differences related with varying irradiances throughout

203 the day or across the canopy. Linear electron transport rate was calculated as in
204 Rosenqvist and van Kooten (2003):

$$205 \text{ ETR} = \text{PPFD} \times \text{abs} \times \phi\text{PSII} \times 0.5 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

206 where PPFD is the photosynthetically photon flux density, abs is leaf absorptance (0.8),
207 ϕPSII is effective photosystem II quantum yield and 0.5 is a factor considering that 2
208 photons are absorbed by each transported electron (and assuming an 1:1 photosystem II/
209 photosystem I ratio). The factor 0.8 (leaf absorptance) is typical for non-senescent leaves
210 of maize (Acciaresi *et al.*, 2014).

211 Stomatal conductance measurements were taken with a Porometer SC-1 (Decagon,
212 USA) in the abaxial side of the leaf, in the same fully illuminated leaf spots used for
213 ETR measurements.

214

215 *Biomass, yield and yield components*

216 In both seasons, destructive samplings were made at HOR at physiological maturity for
217 dry matter determinations. In each subplot, 6 previously tagged plants were harvested
218 and dissected in three parts: (i) stalks with leaf sheaths and tassels, (ii) leaf blades and
219 (iii) ears. All parts were dried in a forced-air oven at 60 °C to constant weight and
220 weighed. Aboveground plant biomass was estimated as the sum of stalks, leaf blades
221 and ears.

222 Yield was estimated by harvesting 20 ears from consecutive plants within the central
223 rows of each plot. No barren plants were found in any of the experiments. Ears were
224 threshed manually, grains were weighed, and an aliquot was oven-dried to constant
225 weight to calculate the percentage of grain moisture in order to express yield at 0%
226 moisture. Mean individual kernel weight (KW) was estimated by counting and
227 weighting grains of each plant harvested for biomass. Kernel number per plant (KNP)
228 was estimated on the basis of KW and grain yield of 20 plants per plot, essentially as in
229 Echarte *et al.* (2000).

230

231 *Samplings in farmer's fields*

232 To complement the experimental results, during 2022-23 growing season, samplings
233 were carried out in 8 farmer's fields across an altitudinal gradient spanning from 2400
234 up to 3400 masl, and within -23.20° and -24.41° latitude (Fig. S1). In all cases, yellow
235 or white maize varieties were sown at conventional sowing dates, irrigated by furrow
236 irrigation and fertilized with goat manure, and no evidence of nutritional or drought

237 stress was observed by the time of visiting the fields. In each field, two separate plots
238 with 4 rows and 1.5 m length were identified around flowering, aiming to represent a
239 variation of plant densities. Plant density was separately estimated for each of the
240 central rows of each plot by counting the total number of plants in the harvested row
241 and the adjacent rows at each side and dividing it by the area occupied by these plants
242 (i.e., 1.5 m length x 0.70 distance between rows x 3 rows). At maturity, all the ears in
243 each of the central rows of each plot were separately harvested, threshed manually,
244 dried until constant weight and weighed. The number of grains per ear was counted and
245 the kernel weight was estimated on the basis of yield per plant and kernel number per
246 plant. Thus, a maximum of 4 data of yield and plant density was available in each
247 farmer field although for different reasons (usually bird attack) some plots were lost in
248 some fields.

249

250 *Statistical analyses*

251 Data were analysed using the STATISTICA 7.1 Software (Stat-Soft, Inc., Tulsa,
252 Oklahoma, USA). Treatments and interaction between them were analysed by ANOVA,
253 and the Levene's test was used to corroborate the assumptions of the model. Each site
254 was analysed independently because of different measurement times except when
255 specifically stated. Plant density, genotype (at HOR) and block were considered fixed
256 factors and each independent variable was analysed separately. For variables
257 comprising different leaves of the canopy or different moments during the day, the leaf
258 position and/or the moment of the day were also treated as fixed factors. When
259 interaction among factors was detected, the LSD test ($P < 0.05$) was used to identify
260 homogenous groups. The significance of regressions was assessed through the F-test
261 ($P < 0.05$).

262

263 **RESULTS**

264

265 *Environmental variation and phenological development*

266 The increase in altitude from 2380 masl at HOR to 3350 at ERO implied an important
267 decrease in T. During 2019-20, medium T during the first 150 days of the cycle was
268 33% higher at HOR compared with ERO (Fig. 1A, B) whereas differences in minimum
269 T were even larger (+40% at HOR). Regarding chilling stress ($< 10^{\circ}\text{C}$, Waqas *et al.*,
270 2021), during the first 150 days of the cycle, only 7 days with minimum T below 10°C

271 were registered at HOR whereas at ERO, there were 94 days out of 150 with minimum
272 T below 10°C. Thus, at ERO, apart from lower medium T, plants may have also
273 experienced critically low minimum temperatures. As expected, T differences delayed
274 phenological development at the highest altitude site, ERO, where the crop reached
275 silking 39 days later than at HOR in 2019-20 (Fig. 1A, B). Nonetheless, much lower
276 thermal time was required to achieve a given phenological stage at ERO: for example,
277 V6 was reached at 697 °C.d at HOR but at 458 °C.d at ERO. Thus, thermal time
278 requirements were reduced when lower temperatures were experienced.

279 Comparing both seasons at HOR, medium and minimum T were higher during the
280 2019-20 growing season compared with 2020-21, and this was accentuated during the
281 reproductive stage (+16 and +22% higher medium and minimum T in 2019-20 averaged
282 from silking until 40 days after silking, Fig. 1A, C). Cumulative solar radiation was also
283 higher in the 2019-20 growing season, with 11% higher solar radiation accumulated
284 until silking and 8% higher solar radiation accumulated from silking until maturity (Fig.
285 1D).

286

287 *Leaf area index and light interception*

288 The increase in plant density increased LAI and light interception with a varying
289 intensity depending on the environment. During the first season at HOR, no significant
290 effect of plant density was detected for LAI or light interception at 86 DAS (Fig. 2A),
291 only a minor advantage at 65 DAS (+17% higher LAI at high density, $P < 0.1$, not
292 shown). By contrast, at ERO, the increase in plant density improved LAI by 75 DAS
293 resulting in a 40% increase in light interception (Fig. 2B). Overall, individual leaf size
294 was larger at ERO compared with HOR (Fig. S2), with a declining trend towards later-
295 developed leaves. Thus, the increase in altitude drastically reduced the LAI achieved by
296 the crop, but this was partially offset by the increase in plant density.

297 During the 2020-21 growing season at HOR, the higher plant density significantly
298 increased LAI of both genotypes from 28 DAS until 153 DAS (Fig. 2C). In relative
299 terms, this increase was higher during early crop stages (>50% higher LAI until 50
300 DAS), was maintained around 40% thereafter, and tend to diminish towards the end of
301 the growing period due to a more accelerated canopy senescence at higher plant density.
302 Light interception at midday was significantly improved by plant density until 78 DAS,
303 with no significant effects thereafter. This is consistent with the crop achieving LAI
304 close to 4 by 80 DAS at the lower plant density, which is usually considered a critical

305 value to maximize light interception in maize. Comparing genotypes, white corn
306 achieved significantly higher LAI from 70 DAS onwards, regardless of plant density.
307 However, light interception was slightly but significantly higher in yellow corn, from 64
308 DAS until 96 DAS, which related to a more planophile leaf habit in yellow corn (Fig.
309 S3). Thus, increasing plant density beyond values conventionally used by farmers
310 resulted in an important increase in LAI and light interception during early stages at
311 ERO (3300 masl) and at HOR during 2020-21, but not at HOR during 2019-20 where
312 highest temperatures during the vegetative period were experienced.

313

314 *Leaf traits*

315 Different leaf traits were analysed in 2019-20 around 96-98 DAS at both sites, allowing
316 a representative statistical comparison. Specific leaf area differed between sites
317 depending on the plant density, being significantly higher at HOR at high plant density
318 with no differences between sites at low density (Table 1). The increase in plant density
319 resulted in higher specific leaf area at HOR (*i.e.*, thinner leaves), but, surprisingly, the
320 opposite was true at ERO. Differences were also detected depending on the leaf position
321 with generally higher specific leaf area at basal leaves (Table 1).

322 Leaf chlorophyll content was estimated on the basis of SPAD values ('greenness') and
323 resembled the differences found for specific leaf area. Significantly higher SPAD values
324 were achieved at ERO (in line with thicker leaves), whereas at HOR, the increase in
325 plant density further reduced SPAD values, consistent with the increase in specific leaf
326 area (*i.e.*, thinner leaves) (Table 1). The SPAD value also changed significantly
327 depending on the leaf position with generally lower SPAD values in apical leaves
328 compared with leaves in middle or basal positions at both sites (Table 1).

329 Leaf %N and leaf N content were also significantly higher at ERO, with no interaction
330 with plant density (Table 1). While higher leaf N content could be partially attributed to
331 thicker leaves at ERO (+8% compared with HOR), relative differences were much
332 greater for N content (+39% compared with HOR). At both sites, apical and middle-
333 positioned leaves had higher N content than basal leaves (Table 1). Overall, several leaf
334 traits differed between sites with a trend to thicker leaves, with higher chlorophyll and
335 N content at the higher altitude site.

336

337 *Photosynthetic rates and stomatal conductance*

338 Photosynthetic electron transport rate (ETR) and stomatal conductance (gs) were
339 measured throughout the day in illuminated leaf spots of 3 leaves representing different
340 positions within the canopy. Because ETR values are usually related with the incoming
341 photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) at the site of measurement, PAR values were
342 also registered but are not representative of the zenithal incoming PAR at those canopy
343 levels or times of the day. Throughout the day, no variation was found at HOR (Fig.
344 3A) whereas at ERO, ETR was significantly lower at the morning, increasing by 15% at
345 midday and by 37% at the afternoon, with no evident relationship with PAR (Fig. 3C).
346 Regarding the leaf position, at HOR, ETR was significantly lower in the basal leaf at
347 high plant density (72 vs. 99 $\mu\text{moles e}^- \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for the rest of the leaves) but, except for
348 this, no significant differences were detected between leaves, despite slightly higher
349 (+11%) incoming PAR at basal and middle leaves (Fig. 3B). By contrast, at ERO, ETR
350 was +19% higher in basal and middle leaves compared with apical leaves, which may
351 partially relate to their +6% higher incoming PAR (Fig. 3D), likely related with the
352 usually more planophile leaf angle. Comparing sites, ETR was higher at ERO than at
353 HOR, especially at midday (+23%) and at the afternoon (+34%), and especially in low
354 (+30%) and middle positioned leaves (+24%) (based on comparisons in Fig. 3). Overall,
355 a higher photosynthetic potential was achieved at ERO but also a much higher variation
356 throughout the day.

357 Stomatal conductance varied throughout the day at both sites. At HOR, gs was +44%
358 higher at the morning than later in the day (Fig. 4A) with no apparent effect on ETR
359 which was unchanged throughout the day (Fig. 3A). Similarly, at ERO, gs decreased
360 throughout the day with +53% higher gs at the morning and midday compared with the
361 afternoon (Fig. 4C), with no evident relationship with ETR, which was highest at the
362 afternoon (Fig. 3C). Regarding leaf position, at HOR gs was +38% higher at mid and
363 apical leaves compared with the basal leaf (Fig. 4B) but all the leaves achieved similar
364 ETR (Fig. 3B). Also at ERO, gs was higher (+26%) at mid and apical leaves compared
365 with the basal leaf (Fig. 4D) with no evident relationship with ETR, which was highest
366 in basal and mid leaves (Fig. 3D). Thus, overall, ETR differences throughout the day
367 and across leaf positions showed no evident relationship with gs variation.

368

369 *Biomass, yield and yield components*

370 Biomass and yield data were obtained from two independent experiments at HOR.
371 Between experiments, yields were 32% higher in the first season but this was not due to

372 increased biomass accumulation, which was larger in the second season (+59%, Table
373 2). Between yield components, a non-significant trend showed that kernel number was
374 more affected (-13%) than kernel weight (-4%) in the second season compared with the
375 first season.

376 Increasing plant density from 5.7 to 8.6 plants m⁻² did not improve yield or modified
377 yield components in 2019-20, whereas in 2020-21 a +26% yield gain was obtained by
378 increasing plant density in both genotypes (Table 2). This was related with a +28%
379 increase in kernel number that did not substantially affect kernel weight (-4%) and with
380 +22% biomass accumulation. Comparing genotypes, white corn exhibited constitutively
381 higher kernel weights and a non-significant trend to higher yields across seasons and
382 plant densities (Table 2). Thus, yield benefits were obtained by increasing plant density
383 in the second season, when overall lower temperatures were experienced and lower
384 yields were attained.

385

386 *Yield response to plant density in farmer's fields*

387 Plant density and yield data were also obtained from samplings in 8 farmer's fields
388 within an altitudinal range spanning from 2400 up to 3400 masl during the 2022-23
389 growing season. A wide range of plant densities were explored across farms, with a
390 minimum of 6 and a maximum of 15 pl m⁻². The expected significant relationship
391 between plant density and yield per plant was found (Fig. 5A, $r^2=0.57^{***}$). Based on
392 the linear equation obtained from this relationship, it was possible to estimate an
393 expected yield per plant at each density and with this, an optimum yield of 3650 kg ha⁻¹
394 being achieved at 10 pl m⁻² (inset in Fig. 5A). Regarding yield components, kernel
395 number m⁻² was positively related to plant density ($r^2= 0.40^{**}$, Fig. 5B) with no
396 evidence of stagnation even at 15 pl m⁻². By contrast, kernel weight was negatively
397 related to plant density ($r^2= 0.41^{**}$, Fig. 5C). Data belonging to highest altitude
398 locations (empty symbols in Fig. 5) usually located above the trend line in Fig. 5B and
399 below the trend line in Fig. 5C, suggesting that, as altitude increases, increasing plant
400 densities result in relatively higher gains in grains m⁻² and higher penalties over kernel
401 weight. Thus, in these high altitude environments, kernel weight is the yield component
402 clearly most affected by increases in plant density whereas no apparent detrimental
403 effect is seen for kernel number even at very high plant densities as 15 pl m⁻².

404

405 **DISCUSSION**

406

407 *Phenological development*

408 As expected, the lower temperatures associated with increased altitude at ERO had an
409 important effect delaying crop phenology, with 39 additional days being required to
410 achieve R1 compared with HOR. Similarly, for landraces grown in Mexico in sites at
411 1550 and 2050 masl, up to 50 extra days were required to achieve the V16 stage at 2050
412 masl (Pace, 2019). However, these extra days did not fully compensate for growing
413 degree days: 297°C.d less were required to achieve the R1 stage at ERO compared with
414 HOR in our work. Similarly, 200°C.d less were required to complete the crop cycle in
415 sites with the same photoperiod and differing in only 400 m of altitude (Jiang *et al.*,
416 1999). This is consistent with environmental modulation of the plastochron (Padilla and
417 Otegui, 2005) and the phyllocron in maize (Tsimba *et al.*, 2013a; Riva-Roveda *et al.*,
418 2016). The phyllocron is decreased with lower temperatures within the range of 12.5-
419 25.5 °C (explored in our study) and also by increased solar radiation (Birch *et al.*,
420 1998), whereas higher proportion of UV-B apparently does not affect development
421 (Kakani *et al.*, 2003). Overall, the increase in altitude delayed phenological
422 development but also, drastically reduced the thermal time requirements in the maize
423 genotype studied in our work.

424

425 *Leaf area index and light interception*

426 Leaf area index and light interception were greatly reduced at the highest altitude site in
427 line with previous reports (Cooper, 1979). While both delayed phenological
428 development and reduced leaf size could account for these differences, here, leaf size
429 was higher at ERO, at least for early-developed leaves (Fig. S2) which has been
430 explained as a result of prolonged duration of leaf expansion (Cooper, 1979; Laffitte
431 and Edmeades, 1997). Nonetheless, very low temperatures were explored in our work at
432 the highest altitude site (>90 days with minimum T below 10°C during the vegetative
433 period, Fig. 1B) and relatively mild chilling temperatures (14/10°C) can reduce leaf size
434 both through effects over cell division and expansion (Louarn *et al.*, 2010). Thus, both
435 effects, prolonged duration of leaf expansion and chilling affecting leaf expansion are
436 likely interacting in opposite directions, finally increasing (as here) or decreasing leaf
437 size at higher altitudes.

438 The increase in plant density improved light interception by 75 DAS at ERO (Fig. 2B),
439 and until 78 DAS at HOR in the second season (Fig. 2D), which coincided with the crop

440 achieving a LAI of 4 at low density (Fig. 2C), around the critical value for maize.
441 Lower temperatures during the vegetative period at ERO (Fig. 1B), or a shorter
442 vegetative period at HOR also combined with slightly lower temperatures (Fig. 1C),
443 limited canopy development allowing plant density advantages in LAI and light
444 interception to be expressed. By contrast, during 2019-20 at HOR, higher temperatures
445 and a longer duration of the vegetative period (Fig. 1A) allowed a larger canopy to be
446 developed, with no advantages of increased plant density related with a trend to reduced
447 leaf size (not shown). Previous works have shown that leaf size is reduced with
448 increasing plant density, but still LAI usually increases up to 10-12 plants m⁻² except in
449 very specific genotype x environment combinations (Madonni *et al.*, 2001). Thus, in
450 these high altitude environments, increasing plant density can improve LAI and light
451 interception during the vegetative period especially under cooler temperatures (ERO
452 2019-20) or shorter vegetative periods (HOR 2020-21) than those experienced at HOR
453 2019-20.

454

455 *Leaf traits*

456 Many leaf traits changed between sites and plant densities. Overall, thicker leaves were
457 attained at ERO (at high density, Table 1), which was not an outcome of decreased leaf
458 size (Fig S2). Consistent with this, specific leaf area is decreased in leaves developed at
459 low T (Riva-Roveda *et al.*, 2016; Zhou *et al.*, 2020) and in maize lines from cool
460 temperate regions compared with lines from warmer origin (Verheul *et al.*, 1996).
461 Increased light penetration in the canopy could explain the thicker leaves at ERO,
462 whereas at HOR, increased shading resulted in higher specific leaf area (Yabiku *et al.*,
463 2020) further augmented by high plant density (Table 1) in line with other works (Yang
464 *et al.*, 2022). Other factors could also be involved, such as increased leaf sugar
465 accumulation decreasing specific leaf area which has been reported in leaves developed
466 under lower T (Riva-Roveda *et al.*, 2016).

467 Higher SPAD values (+36%) and N contents on a dry mass basis (+39%) were achieved
468 at ERO compared to HOR (Table 1), which was not simply an outcome of thicker
469 leaves since relative differences for specific leaf area were much lower (8% higher at
470 HOR). Low temperatures usually decrease chlorophyll and N content in maize (Nie *et al.*,
471 1995; Leipner *et al.*, 1997; Pasini *et al.*, 2005) thus are unlikely to explain
472 differences between sites in our work. By contrast, increased exposure to UV-B
473 radiation results in higher chlorophyll concentration (Zancan *et al.*, 2006; Jovanic *et al.*,

474 2022) and leaf protein concentration (Tevini *et al.*, 1981) although these works did not
475 explore the interaction with low T. Further work is needed to better assess the potential
476 effects of UV-B radiation combined with lower temperatures over leaf traits, using
477 realistic conditions as found in a high altitude environment as ERO. In any case, thicker
478 leaves, with higher protein content as found in ERO could partially compensate the
479 decreased LAI with a higher photosynthetic potential.

480

481 *Photosynthesis and stomatal conductance*

482 Photosynthesis was estimated through ETR, which in C₄ species correlates closely with
483 CO₂ assimilation (Earl and Tollenaar, 1999). Because our measurements were made at
484 full irradiance, the ETR obtained here is a proxy of the photosynthetic potential of the
485 leaves in each treatment and condition. At HOR, ETR was unchanged throughout the
486 day (Fig. 3A) with minimum T during the days of measurement always above 15°C
487 (Fig. 1A). By contrast, at ERO, ETR progressively increased throughout the day, with
488 37% higher ETR at the afternoon compared with the morning (Fig. 3C) and minimum T
489 during the days of measurements below 8.3°C (Fig. 1B). Consistent with this, low night
490 T (<10°C) can reduce maize photosynthesis up to 30% (Dwyer and Tollenaar, 1989;
491 Ying *et al.*, 2000), chlorophyll fluorescence parameters such as ETR being directly
492 affected (Ying *et al.*, 2000). On the basis of maximum ETR achieved at each site, leaves
493 at ERO showed a higher photosynthetic potential and no penalties of increased plant
494 density.

495 Our results also suggest that the rate of recovery from low night T could be slow at high
496 altitude sites such as ERO (highest ETR at the afternoon, Fig. 3C), with implications
497 over photosynthetic water use efficiency (*i.e.* the quotient between photosynthesis and
498 transpiration rate), as at the same location, maximum gs was achieved in the early
499 morning (+60% compared with the afternoon, Fig. 4C). Exploring genotypic differences
500 in rates of recovery from low night T deserves further attention considering the potential
501 implications on water use efficiency in these irrigated cropping systems. On the other
502 hand, our results show that highest ETR rates were achieved at the highest altitude site
503 (Fig. 3A vs. 3C at the afternoon) at very similar stomatal conductance rates (Fig. 4A vs.
504 4C at the afternoon), suggesting that the decrease in CO₂ partial pressure with
505 increasing altitude (Körner, 2007) was not a major constrain here.

506

507 *Biomass, yield and yield components*

508 It is generally accepted that environments with a higher yield potential require higher
509 planting densities to optimize yields (Tokatlidis *et al.*, 2011). However, there are some
510 exceptions to this rule. For example, in late sowings, maize yields are usually decreased
511 but optimum plant density can be similar or even higher compared with earlier sowings
512 (Zhai *et al.*, 2021; Djaman *et al.*, 2022). In our work, higher yields were achieved in the
513 first experiment at HOR but no response to plant density was obtained (6356 kg ha⁻¹,
514 Table 2), whereas in the second experiment, a later sowing date combined with cooler
515 temperatures and lower solar radiation likely resulted in lower yields (4821 kg ha⁻¹,
516 Table 2) but also in a positive response to increased plant density (+26% in both
517 genotypes). Results obtained from farmer's fields (between 2400 and 3400 masl, thus
518 higher than HOR) showed a consistent response of yield per plant to increasing plant
519 densities (Fig. 5A), with an estimated maximum yield of around 3600 kg ha⁻¹ being
520 achieved at 10 pl m⁻² (inset in Fig. 5A). Thus, environments with a lower yield potential
521 (either in our second experiment or in farmer's fields) seemed to be benefitted by
522 increases in plant density.

523 The yield improvement at high planting density in the second season was mostly related
524 to kernel number m⁻² (+28%) (Table 2), and was consistent with the larger LAI and
525 light interception achieved before flowering at high density (Fig. 2C, 2D). Similarly,
526 across farmer's fields kernel number m⁻² steadily increased with higher plant density (up
527 to 15 pl m⁻²), with higher altitude locations being usually above the trend line (Fig. 5B).
528 Benefits from increasing plant densities may be, thus, larger under higher altitudes (as it
529 occurs in cool environments, Westgate *et al.*, 1997), improving radiation interception
530 during the critical period, and with this, kernel number (Andrade *et al.*, 1999). On the
531 other hand, reductions in kernel number at low planting density could be compensated
532 for by larger kernels. But this was not observed, either in our second experiment (Table
533 2) or across farmer's fields, where at low planting densities, empty symbols (obtained
534 from higher altitudes) usually located below the trend line (lower ability to compensate
535 low planting densities with higher grain weights, Fig. 5C). According to Zhou *et al.*
536 (2017) low minimum T (<20.7°C) during grain filling combined with a high daily
537 thermal amplitude (T_{max-min}>7°C) can decrease kernel growth rate. In our second
538 experiment, minimum T during the first 30 days after silking were much lower than
539 these (<10.8°C) and the daily thermal amplitude was much higher (T_{max-min}>12°C). The
540 same can be speculated for the higher altitude locations where samplings in farmer's
541 fields were carried out. Consistently, dry matter remobilization from vegetative parts is

542 affected when ear T drops below 16°C (Setter and Flannigan, 1986), possibly
543 explaining the coexisting low yields with high biomass accumulation in the second
544 season. Thus, increasing plant density could be a promising strategy for improving
545 yields in high altitude environments. Further research is needed to understand
546 mechanisms behind penalties on kernel weight; especially, whether higher kernel
547 number can improve biomass allocation to the ear under low temperatures that limit
548 kernel growth rates.

549

550 *Concluding remarks and future prospects*

551 In this work we show that increased altitude in mid-latitude environments of the
552 Northwest of Argentina (3350 masl compared to 2300 masl) drastically delays
553 phenological development, reduces thermal time requirements, and modifies leaf traits
554 increasing leaf thickness and leaf nitrogen content. Whereas a higher photosynthetic
555 potential could be achieved at the highest altitude site this may not be fully exploited
556 due to inhibitory effects of low night T and, apparently, long times of recovery from
557 night chilling. Yield data obtained from experiments at 2300 masl and across farmer's
558 fields within 2400 and 3400 masl indicate that increased plant density beyond those
559 currently recommended could potentially improve yields regardless of the
560 environmental yield potential, with maximum yields of 3650 kg ha⁻¹ achieved at 10 pl
561 m⁻². Main penalties of increased plant densities are related to reductions in kernel
562 weight. Further work is needed to explore the effects of different factors limiting kernel
563 growth rate, such as low temperatures and early frosts, over plant density responses.

564

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571

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579

580 **CONFLICTS OF INTEREST**

581 The authors declare none.

582

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744 **Figure captions**

745

746 Fig. 1: Temperatures during the growing cycle of Andean maize in Hornillos (2380
747 masl) during 2019-20 (A) and 2020-21 (C) and in El Rosal (3350 masl) during 2019-20
748 (B), and solar radiation (MJ m^{-2}) in the three experiments estimated by the SOLCAST
749 satellite database (D). Minimum, mean and maximum temperatures are indicated by
750 dotted, solid and dashed lines, respectively, and the horizontal dashed lines mark the
751 limit for temperatures below 10°C , potentially stressful for maize. Phenological stages,
752 indicated above the “x” axis, are defined based on the scale proposed by Ritchie et al.
753 (1989). In Figs. A and C, the black bar below R1 indicates the chronological time
754 elapsed during the critical period estimated in 400°C bracketing silking (Sadras and
755 Calderini, 2020).

756

757 Fig. 2: Leaf area index and light interception measured at midday in Andean maize at
758 Hornillos (2380 masl) during 2019-20 (A) and 2020-21 (C, D) and at El Rosal (3350
759 masl) during 2019-20 (B) at different plant densities. In (A) measurements were done at
760 86 days after silking (filled bars correspond to yellow corn, empty bars to white corn).
761 In (B) measurements were done at 75 days after silking in yellow corn. In (C) and (D)
762 circles denote low plant density ($5.7 \text{ plants m}^{-2}$), triangles denote high plant density
763 ($8.6 \text{ plants m}^{-2}$), filled symbols denote yellow corn and empty symbols denote white
764 corn. In (C) and (D), empty bars show the relative increase at high plant density
765 compared with low plant density in both genotypes (as no density x genotype
766 interaction for LAI or light interception).

767

768 Fig. 3: Photosynthetic electron transport rate ($\mu\text{moles e}^{-} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, filled bars) and
769 photosynthetically active radiation ($\mu\text{moles photons}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, empty bars) at the leaf
770 spot where measurements were taken in Andean maize at Hornillos (2380 masl, A, B)
771 and at El Rosal (3350 masl, C, D) during 2019-20. In each site, measurements were
772 taken during 2 consecutive days, at the morning, midday and afternoon in plants grown
773 under two contrasting plant densities (5.7 plants and $8.6 \text{ plants m}^{-2}$) and in 3 leaves
774 representing different positions within the canopy. Significant differences during the
775 day are shown in A and C by pooling together plant densities and leaf positions,
776 whereas significant differences between leaf positions are shown in B and D by pooling

777 together plant densities and time of the day. Lines above the bars indicate the standard
778 error and letters show homogeneous groups according to the LSD test ($P < 0.05$).

779

780 Fig. 4: Stomatal conductance ($\text{mmoles H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) at the same leaf spot where
781 photosynthetic electron transport rate measurements were taken in Andean maize at
782 Hornillos (2365 masl, A, B) and at El Rosal (3350 masl, C, D) during 2019-20. In each
783 site, measurements were taken during 2 consecutive days, at the morning, midday and
784 afternoon, in plants grown under two contrasting plant densities (5.7 plants and 8.6
785 plants m^{-2}) and in 3 leaves representing different positions within the canopy.
786 Significant differences during the day are shown in A and C by pooling together plant
787 densities and leaf positions, whereas significant differences between leaf positions are
788 shown in B and D by pooling together plant densities and time of the day. Lines above
789 the bars indicate the standard error and letters show homogeneous groups according to
790 the LSD test ($P < 0.05$).

791

792 Fig. 5: Results obtained from samplings in farmer's fields during 2022-23 growing
793 season: yield per plant (A), kernel number m^{-2} (B) and kernel weight (C) as a function
794 of plant density (estimated by the number of plants in the sampled row and the adjacent
795 rows at each side). Different symbols denote the altitude of each location, whereas each
796 symbol represents the average value of each sampled row (1.5 m length). Inset in (A)
797 shows the expected yield response based on the linear equation obtained between yield
798 per plant and plant density. Asterisks denote significant regressions: **, $P < 0.01$; ***,
799 $P < 0.001$.

Figure

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Figure

Table 1: Specific leaf area ($\text{cm}^2 \text{mg}_{\text{DW}}^{-1}$), SPAD values, N concentration (%) and N content (mg cm^{-2}) of Andean maize at two locations: Hornillos (HOR, 2380 masl) and El Rosal (ERO, 3350 masl) during 2019-20. Leaf traits were measured under two contrasting plant densities (5.7 and 8.6 pl m^{-2}), in 3 leaves representing different positions within the canopy (basal, mid and apical leaves). Statistical significance represented as: *: $P < 0.05$; **: $P < 0.01$ and ***: $P < 0.001$; NS indicates no significant relationship. For each trait, mean values for each significant factor are deployed.

		Specific leaf area ($\text{cm}^2 \text{mg}_{\text{DW}}^{-1}$)	SPAD values	N concentration (%)	N content (mg cm^{-2})	
<i>Location</i>						
	HOR	0.196 a	38.3 b	2.2 a	0.121 b	
	ERO	0.180 b	52.1 a	3.3 b	0.169 a	
<i>Plant density</i>						
	5.7	0.185	46.9 a	2.7	0.149	
	8.6	0.191	43.6 b	2.7	0.141	
<i>Leaf position</i>						
	Lower	0.198 a	46.4 a	2.7	0.135 b	
	Mid	0.182 b	47.5 a	2.7	0.150 a	
	Apical	0.183 b	41.7 b	2.8	0.151 a	
<i>Location x Plant density</i>						
	HOR	5.7	0.183 bc	42.8 b	2.2	0.122
		8.6	0.208 a	33.8 c	2.1	0.120
	ERO	5.7	0.186 b	51.0 a	3.2	0.177
		8.6	0.174 c	53.3 a	3.3	0.160
<i>Location</i>						
		***	***	***	***	
<i>Plant density</i>						
		NS	**	NS	NS	
<i>Leaf position</i>						
		**	***	NS	*	
<i>Location x Plant density</i>						
		***	***	NS	NS	
<i>Location x Leaf position</i>						
		NS	NS	NS	NS	
<i>Plant density x Leaf position</i>						
		NS	NS	NS	NS	
<i>Location x Plant density x Leaf position</i>						
		NS	NS	NS	NS	

Table 2: Yield (kg ha⁻¹), kernel number (KN m⁻²), kernel weight (KW, mg kernel⁻¹) and biomass (kg ha⁻¹) in two genotypes of Andean maize (white and yellow corn) grown at Hornillos (HOR, 2380 masl) during 2019-20 and 2020-21 under two contrasting plant densities (5.7 and 8.6 pl m⁻²). Statistical significance represented as: +: P<0.1; *: P<0.05; **: P<0.01 and ***: P<0.001; NS indicates no significant relationship. For each trait, mean values for each significant factor or interaction among factors are deployed.

		Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	KN m ⁻²	KW (mg kernel ⁻¹)	Biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)
<i>Experiment</i>					
	I	6356 a	1304	511	16100
	II	4821 b	1152	491	25624
<i>Plant density</i>					
	5.7	5245	1091	506	21233
	8.6	5713	1296	487	24820
<i>Genotype</i>					
	Yellow	5251	1274	433 b	22573
	White	5707	1112	560 a	23480
<i>Experiment * Plant density</i>					
I	5.7	6546 a	1301 ab	522	16230 c
I	8.6	6166 ab	1307 ab	501	15970 c
II	5.7	4270 c	1012 a	500	23109 b
II	8.6	5373 b	1292 b	482	28138 a
<i>Plant density * Genotype</i>					
5.7	Yellow	5058	1123	443	21164
5.7	White	5432	1059	569	21302
8.6	Yellow	5443	1425	424	23982
8.6	White	5983	1166	550	25657
<i>Experiment</i>		***	NS	NS	***
<i>Plant density</i>		NS	NS	NS	*
<i>Genotype</i>		NS	NS	***	NS
<i>Experiment x Plant density</i>		*	+	NS	*
<i>Experiment x Genotype</i>		NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Plant density x Genotype</i>		NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Experiment x Plant density x Genotype</i>		NS	NS	NS	NS

Fig. S1: Geographic locations of farmer's fields where samplings were carried out during 2022-23 growing season. Meters above the sea level (masl) are indicated next to the sampling point in the right panel.

Fig. S2: Individual leaf size of fully expanded leaves at Hornillos (HOR, black bars, 2365 masl) and El Rosal (ERO, grey bars, 3350 masl) in yellow corn. Lines above the bars denote the standard error and same letters show homogeneous groups according to LSD ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. S3: Leaf angle (mean of 9 consecutive leaves starting from the 4th leaf below the ear leaf up to the 4th leaf above the ear leaf) measured at HOR in two genotypes (white and yellow corn) at two contrasting plant densities (indicated below the x axis). Leaf angle was measured from the stem to the upper surface of the leaf (thus, higher values indicate a more planophile leaf habit). Lines above the bars denote the standard error and same letters show homogeneous groups according to LSD ($P < 0.05$).

Table S1: Soil properties determined in samples taken in the first 20-40 cm at two locations, Hornillos (HOR, 2380 masl) and El Rosal (ERO, 3350 masl).

	HOR	ERO
<i>Textural composition</i>		
Clay (%)	30	2.5
Silt (%)	17.5	7.5
Sand (%)	52.5	90
Textural classification (USDA)	Sandy loam	Sandy
<i>Chemical properties</i>		
EC (dS m ⁻¹)	1.795	2.38
pH	7.93	7.8
Organic matter (%)	2.83	9.23
Organic carbon (%)	1.64	5.36
Total N (%)	0.16	0.47
C/N Relationship	10	11
Extractable P (mg kg ⁻¹)	4	93
Available K (mg.kg ⁻¹)	316	881
<i>Exchangeable cations</i>		
Calcium (cmol ₍₊₎ .kg ⁻¹)	-	-
Magnesium (cmol ₍₊₎ .kg ⁻¹)	-	-
Sodium (cmol ₍₊₎ .kg ⁻¹)	0.46	0.26
Potassium (cmol ₍₊₎ .kg ⁻¹)	0.81	2.26